

The Influence of Poverty, Village Fund and Village Owned-Income on Village Expenditure Allocation for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs (an Empirical Study of Villages in Sragen District in 2020)

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the influence of Poverty, Village Fund, and Village Owned-Income on Village Expenditure Allocation for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs. The populations of this study is all villages in Sragen Regency and this study utilize purposive sampling method with certain criterias. The hypothesis was tested by multiple linear regression analysis with the coefficient of determination test, F test, and t test. The indicate that Poverty and Village Owned-Income have no effect on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs. However Village Found have an effect on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs. The study suggested that Allocation for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs must be consider the poverty and Village Owned-Income to make accurate and in the next study suggested the village government also consider the poverty and the among Village Owned-Income as consideration on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs.

Keywords: Poverty, Village Expenditures for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs, Village Funds, Village Owned-Income.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Coronavirus outbreak, also known as Covid-19, causes significant turmoil in the all sector offer globe, almost all sectors are affected, resulting in a slowdown in national economic growth, a decrease in state revenue and an increase in spending used for financing. So the government is trying to do economic stability by saving health and focusing on spending for handling Covid-19, as well as carrying out economic recovery including for the business world and affected communities.

In the Indonesian Law Number 1 of 2020 regarding financial policies and a stable financial system for handling the Covid-19 pandemic stating that village funds can be used for prevention pandemic Covid-19 and direct cash assistance. The regulation states that it is necessary to prioritize the use of budget allocations for certain activities, adjust povertyents to allocations the distribution of the transfer budget to the area and village funds with certain criteria. Next on the explanation Indonesian Law also states that what is meant by prioritizing the use of village funds is that village funds can be used, among other things, for direct cash assistance to the population poor in the village and the activities of handling the Covid-19 pandemic (Valentina, 2020).

All levels of government in Indonesia need a classification related to matters that cannot only be handled by the central government. Village is the vanguard in providing services and has a broad scope that is used to manage the community independently. Villages have the right and obligation to manage their own finances based on the potential and resources of the village to enhance community development and empowerment.

People's welfare is one of the main goals of government, which begins with improving the community's economy. To overcome obstacles in the implementation of village government, the implementation of the village government creates a program by providing assistance in the form of Village Funds.

Research on Poverty, Village Funds, Village Owned-Income on village spending has been carried out by many previous researchers. Research on the Poverty, according to Amiyati and Bawono (2018) shows that the poverty has a negative effect on village spending in the Education sector, this is not in line with research by Pratama (2019) which states that the poverty has no effect on spending on community empowerment. Research on Village Funds according to Febriyanti and Bawono (2018) states that Village Funds have no significant effect on Village Expenditures in the Education Sector. This is not in accordance with research from Rismawati (2020) showing that Village Funds have a significant effect on village expenditure. Research on Village Owned-Income on village expenditures, according to Amnan, Sjahrudin and Hardiani (2019) which states that it has no negative and significant effect on village expenditure, this is not in line with the research of Farida, Gunarto, Hasan (2021) stating that Village Owned-Income has a significant effect on village expenditure.

Based on the lack of consistency in previous studies, so the author is interested in doing research on **“The Influence of Poverty, Village Fund and Village Owned-Income on Village Expenditure Allocation for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs (an empirical study of villages in Sragen district in 2020)”**. The difference between this research and before lies in, the variable, time period, and object.

II. HEADINGS

Budget Theory

Budgeting in Public Sector Accounting is a tool used to plan a financial activity in the future, the activity includes development, empowerment and short-term strategy. A budget is planning finance for the future which generally covers a period of one year and is expressed in monetary units (Mahsun, 2006). the budget is a quantitative plan in the form of monetary and non-monetary which is used to translate the goals and strategies of the company into operational units. (Hansen and Mowen (2004: 354)

Governmental Accounting Standards Board (GASB) defines that a budget as a financial operating plan that includes estimated proposed expenditures, and the expected sources of income to finance them within a certain period of time.

Poverty

Poverty is something condition where somebody or a group no capable for fulfil the right basically to maintain and develop their life. Poverty is a condition where a person cannot enjoy all kinds of choices and opportunities in fulfill basic needs such as not being able to meet health, decent living standards, freedom, price self-esteem and respect like everyone else. (World Bank;2015)

Hypothesis 1 (H1). There is an influence of Poverty Level on Expenditure Allocation for Disaster Management, Emergencies and Urgent Villages in Villages in Sragen Regency.

Village Fund

In Indonesian Law number 47 Year 2015, Village Funds are funds from the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget allocated to villages transferred through the Regency or City Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget, for funding government administration, implementation of development, development of community and community empowerment. The Priority of using of Village Funds aims to fund development and empowerment of the community so that welfare can be improved later.

Hypothesis 2 (H2). There is an influence of Village Funds on Expenditure Allocation for Disaster Management, Emergencies and Village Urges in Villages in Sragen Regency.

Village Owned-Income

Permendagri Number 20 of 2018, Village Owned-Income is the result of business, assets, self-help, participation and mutual cooperation, and other Village Owned-Income. Village Owned-Income includes all receipts fund, one budget year that belongs to the village and is not returned by the village.

Hypothesis 3 (H3). There is an influence of Village Owned-Income on Expenditure Allocation for Disaster Management, Emergencies and Village Urges in Villages in Sragen Regency

III. INDENTATIONS AND EQUATIONS

Research Design

This research uses quantitative research methods with descriptive approach methods, quantitative methods are used to analyze the influence Poverty, Village Fund and Village Owned-Income on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs.

Population and sample

The population in this study is all village in Sragen Regency consists 196 Villages from 20 Districts (<http://sragen.kab.go.id>). After eliminating data, reseachers used 180 Villages as sample in this study.

Types and data Sources

This study used secondary data obtained from the Community and Village Empowerment Office (PMD) and the Social Service. The data obtained is in the form of 2020 Village Revenue and Expenditure Budget Realization Report (APBDesa) data, and Poverty data.

Data analysis method

Hypothesis test study it uses multiple linear regression analysis. This analysis is used to determine the effect of Poverty Level, Village Fund and Village Owned-Income on the allocation of Village Expenditures for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs. the regression model in this study are:

$$BPBKDM = \alpha + b1 TM + b2 DD + b3 PADesa + e$$

Information:

BPBKDM =Village Expenditures for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs

TM = Poverty

DD = Village Funds

PADesa =Village Owned-Income

a =Regression Constant

b1, b2, b3 =Regression Coefficient

e = errors

IV. FIGURES AND TABLES

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Results of Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Means	std. Deviation
Poverty	180	192.00	1206.00	537.2444	182.55002
Village Fund	180	697148913.00	1476056285.00	900744191.0722	155010246.74983
Village Owned-Income	180	727600.00	934212082.00	170312050.3444	163673646.34487

BPBKDM	180	96390000.00	917225000.00	454670186.33	123860396.36
				33	846
Valid N	180				

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

The Foverty Population has the lowest number of 192, namely Kadipiro Village and the highest number of 1,206, namely Kalangan Village. The mean value of the number of poor people is 537.2444 and the standard deviation is 182.55002.

The Village Fund variable has the lowest amount of IDR697,148,913.00, namely Suwatu Village, and the highest amount is IDR 1,476,056,285.00, namely Jekawal Village. The mean value of the Village Fund is IDR 900,744,191.0722 and a standard deviation of IDR 155.010.246.74983.

Village Owned-Income Variable has the lowest amount of IDR 727,600.00, namely Jati Village, and the highest amount of IDR 934,212,082.00, namely Gringging Village. The mean value of Village Owned-Income is IDR 170,312,050.3444 and a standard deviation of IDR 1.636.736.46,34487.

Variable Village Expenditures for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs have the lowest amount of IDR96,390,000.00, namely Bagor Village and has the highest amount of IDR 917,225,000.00, namely Jekawal Village. mean valueVillage Expenditures for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs amount to IDR454,670,186.3333 and a standard deviation of IDR 123.860.396,36846.

Classic Assumption Test

Normality Test

Table 2. Normality Test Results

<i>Kolmogorov-Smirnov(KS)</i>	<i>asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	Information
1,270	0.080	normally distributed

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

Normality test is tested using statistical tests non parametric Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS). Based on the results of the normality test, it is known that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) value is 1.255 and the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.080. Significance value 0.080 > 0.05 so it can be interpreted that the data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results

Variable	<i>tolerance</i>	<i>VIF</i>	Information
Poverty	0.995	1.005	Multicollinearity Does Not Occur
Village Fund	0.931	1,074	Multicollinearity Does Not Occur
Village Owned-Income	0.930	1.075	Multicollinearity Does Not Occur

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test in table 3 it is known that all variables have a tolerance value ≥ 0.10 and a VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value ≤ 10 , so it can be concluded that the data is free from symptoms of multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity test

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variable	Sig.	Information
Poverty	0.891	There is no heteroscedasticity
Village Fund	0.206	There is no heteroscedasticity
Village Owned-Income	0.880	There is no heteroscedasticity

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

The heteroscedasticity test uses the Rank Spearman correlation coefficient test, namely to detect whether there are symptoms of heteroscedasticity. Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test in table 4 it is known that all variables have a significance value of 0.05, so it can be concluded that the data is free of heteroscedasticity.

Autocorrelation test

Table 5. Autocorrelation Test Results

Variables	Durbin Watson	Information
Poverty	1.365	Autocorrelation does not occur
Village Fund		
Village Owned-Income		

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

Based on the results of the autocorrelation test in table 5, it is known that the Durbin Watson value is 1.365, and the DW value lies between -2 to +2, so it can be concluded that the data does not have autocorrelation.

Hypothesis Testing

Analysis of Multiple Linear Regression Equation

Table 6. Hypothesis Testing

Variables	tcount	Sig.	Information
(Constant)	-1,909	0.058	
Poverty	0.569	0.570	Not Significant
Village Fund	13,241	0.000	Significant
Village Owned-Income	1,522	0.130	Not Significant

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

Based on the results of multiple linear regression tests in table 6, the regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$BPBKDM = -91,222,545.021 + 20545.576 TM + 0.528 DD + 0.063 Village\ Owned-Income + e$$

The interpretation of the results of the multiple linear regression test is as follows:

- a) Constant value of -91,222,545.021 has a negative value, so if the Poverty, DD, and Village Owned-Income variables have a fixed value, and Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs decrease by -91,222,545.021.
- b) The Poverty coefficient value is 20545.576 with a positive value. This shows that the Poverty variable has increased by one unit, Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs experienced an increase of 20545.576. If the Poverty variable has decreased by one unit, then Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs have decreased by 20545.576.
- c) The Village Funds coefficient value of 0.582 is positive, meaning that if the DD variable increases by one unit, then Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs. will increase by 0.582. If the DD variable has decreased by one unit, Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs have decreased by 0.582.
- d) The Village Owned-Income Coefficient value of 0.63 is positive, meaning that if the Village Owned-Income variable increases by one unit, then Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs will increase by 0.582. If the Village Owned-Income variable has decreased by one unit, Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs has decreased by 0.582.

Determination Coefficient Test

Table 7. Determination Coefficient Test

R	R Square	Dusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
0.710	0.505	0.496	87916377,83053

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

Based on table 7 for the Adjusted R square value of 0.496 or 49.6%. This shows that Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs can be explained by 49.6% by the independent variables namely Poverty Level, Village Fund, and Village Owned-Income. While the remaining 50.4% is explained by other factors outside the variables studied.

Model Fisibility Test (F-Test)

Table 8. Determination Coefficient Test

Fcount	Ftable	Sig.	Information
59,762	2.66	0.000	Influence simultaneously

Data source: Secondary data processed by researchers, 2023

Based on table 8 it can be seen that $F_{count} > F_{table}$ is $59.762 > 2.66$ and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the variables Poverty Level, Village Fund, and Village Owned-Income (PAD) simultaneously affect Expenditures Village Disaster Management Sector, Emergency Conditions and Urgent Village.

Statistics Test

Based on table 6 it can be concluded that:

- The Poverty Level variable has a significance value greater than the level of significance, namely $0.570 > 0.05$ and a t_{count} of 0.569 which is smaller than the t_{table} of 2.34748. It can be concluded that partially the Poverty Level has no significant effect on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and emergencies Affairs. So that the first hypothesis (H1) is rejected.
- The Village Fund variable has a significance value less than the level of significance of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a t_{count} of 13.241 is greater than a t_{table} of 2.34748. This shows that partially the Village Fund has a significant positive effect on Village Expenditure in the Field of Disaster Management, Emergency Conditions and Village Urges. So can be interpreted that the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

The Village Owned-Income variable has a significance value greater than the level of significance, namely $0.130 > 0.05$ and a t_{count} of 1.552 which is smaller than the t_{table} of 2.34748. It can be concluded that partially Original Village Income has no

V. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion of the data, the results of this study can be concluded as follows:

- The results of the partial test show that the poverty level has no effect on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs.
- The partial test results show that the Village Fund has a significant positive effect on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs.
- The partial test results show that Village Owned-Income has no effect on Village Expenditure for Disaster Management and Emergencies Affairs.

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